

Treatment Of Slaughterhouse Wastewater By Upflow Anaerobic Hybrid Reactor At Pilot Scale

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The wastewater discharged by slaughterhouse industries is categorized mainly by high COD, high BOD, high suspended and complex mixture of fats, proteins and fibres which needs systematic treatment before the disposal. In the present study, the performance of 3.26 L upflows anaerobic hybrid reactor treating the slaughterhouse wastewater with polyvinyl chloride (PVC) uses as filter media was investigated. For seeding, the reactor is inoculated with activated sludge from a upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactor treating the slaughterhouse wastewater. After seeding, the reactor with maintained, inlet flow of 135.72 mL/hr is loaded with different dilution ratios of the sample (1/10, 1/6, 1/4 and 1/1 or undiluted) with different COD loadings (9.281 kg.COD/m³ day, 10.149 kg.COD/m³ day, 9.263 kg.COD/m³ day and 11.210 kg.COD/m³ day) with HRT of 24 hr and achieved maximum COD removal efficiency upto 73.32% at COD loading of 11.210 kg.COD/m³ day. Alongwith the COD, other required parameters, such as phosphorus, BOD, TSS, VSS and volatile acid as acetic acid are also found out to check the efficiency of the reactor.

KEYWORDS

Slaughterhouse waste, Anaerobic digestion, Anaerobic filter, UASB reactor, Chemical oxygen demand

1. INTRODUCTION

In India alongwith many other countries, the production of poultry meat has been increasing day by day. Slaughterhouse produces a huge amount of wastewater with high protein, fat and grease content. Surface and groundwater pollution alongwith odour, mosquito and fly nuisance are end results by these process practices. The effluent from slaughterhouse contains high TSS and BOD₅ of 1510-3232 mg/L and 3673-6404 mg/L, respectively [1]. The slaughterhouse wastewater is very suitable for the treatment anaerobically because of the high concentration of biodegradable organics, alkalinity, TSS and phosphorus. It does not have toxic compounds and has a warm temperature (around 30°C). Anaerobic digestion results in high organic removal while producing energy in the form of methane. It generates a low quantity of sludge which does not require aeration. Anaerobic bacteria can survive without food for long periods of time which is an important factor for small slaughterhouses that operate only a few days a week [1,2]. The anaerobic process has been studied over the years from many points of view [3]. As a result, both the conventional and unconventional as-

pects of such a process are adequately known [4,5,6,7,8,9].

In order to obtain a good removal of organic matter during anaerobic digestion, it is necessary to properly select the system to be implemented. In this frame, the attached growth reactors are systems where bacteria are attached to an inert support, developing a biofilm [10]. This kind of reactor is widely used for the food industry wastewater treatment [11,12,13]. There are many configurations of attached growth reactors: fluidized bed reactors, anaerobic expanded bed reactors and upflow packed bed reactors (UPBR) or filters (UPBF) [13,14,15,16,17]. The number of waste products discharged from processing operations in a poultry plant may range from 5-10 gallons per bird with 7 gallons is considered as a typical value. Meat processing wastewater is typically organic in nature; BOD is higher than domestic sewage and a high amount of suspended solids and floating matters such as scum and grease. Day by day due to the increasing usage of water, the wastewater generation is also very high and also has a high concentration of pollutants varying in very high range. Depending upon the extent of treatment needed poultry processors to have the option of utilizing physical, chemical and biological treatment systems. Each system type exhibits unique treatment advantages and operational difficulties.

Figure 1. (a) Reactor setup, (b) PVC filter media and (c) porous plate

Among the various treatment systems, high rate anaerobic reactors are projected nearly as good different and effective system attributable to its various benefits, like low initial and operational prices, smaller area necessities, high organic removal potency and low sludge production, combined with a net energy profit through the production of biogas [3,5,18]. Anaerobic filters (AF) are thought of as a most helpful system, at high organic loading rates (OLR) for the treatment of low and high strength wastewaters because of the provision of enormous biomass and consistent performance [7,8,19]. Guerrero observed that at an OLR of 1.62-5.26 kg/m³/day treatment efficiencies of 80-90% and HRT of 4.41-12.22 days for the treating fish meal processing wastewater using PVC media [20]. Tritt treated the slaughterhouse wastewater using two fixed bed reactors using 2 different media at an OLR of 2-18.5 kg/m³/day and hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 5-0.5 day [21]. It was seen that the COD removal efficiencies of 85-30% (bamboo) and 80-27% (bones) were achieved [10, 22]. Delpozo worked on the application of a fixed film reactor for the treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater and result in the COD removal efficiencies of 85-95% at an OLR of 8 kg/m³/day.

However, it was concluded that at high OLR (35 kg/m³/day) results in lower removal efficiencies of 55-75% [22]. Borja studied the performance assessment of AF with a fluidized bed reactor (FBR) for the treatment of Palm Oil Mill effluent and attained the maximum OLR of 20 kg/m³/day for AF without clogging [23]. Ruiz assesses the performance of an upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) with AF reactor and found that at high OLR lower removal efficiencies in AF was seen as compared to UASB. The presence of biomass in anaerobic filters was in both form, as attached film and suspended flocs/granules [7,8]. Jawed observed

that the collection of sludge solids in the packing media was irregular in the downflow anaerobic filter (DAF) as compared to that in an upflow anaerobic filter (UAF) [7]. Apart from the attached microbial film, granular sludge also plays a crucial role in the handling of anaerobic filters. Granules were seen in anaerobic filters and the development of granules is because of microbial and hydraulic selection pressure. The microbial choice is governed by the concentration of substrate, type of substrate and various other environmental factors [24,25].

To meet the water pollution control standards additional treatment is required. As indicated above, anaerobic treatment is a good option for a first stage biological treatment of this wastewater [19,22]. The aim of this study was to determine the removal efficiency and performance of the anaerobic degradation at ambient temperature in a UASB reactor applied for the treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater, previously submitted to screening and settling.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Experimental setup

In this study, the acrylic plastic cylindrical column was used as an anaerobic hybrid reactor at the pilot scale. The reactor had an internal diameter of 9.4 cm, an external diameter of 10 cm and a height of 80 cm results in a total volume of 3.26 L with a top of gas headspace for gas collection (Figure 1a). The waste feed inlet was made in such a way that the inlet was provided upside down which permit the wastewater to enters from the base, under the bed of sludge zone and evenly distributed in an upward direction. Four ports of 2.5 cm diameter are provided on one side of the reactor and one bottom port is provided on another

Figure 2. Flowchart of upflow anaerobic hybrid reactor

side for the inlet. Space between the top three ports is 23 cm (end to end) and spacing between last and second last port is 19.5 cm. The topmost porthole is provided at 1.5 cm downward from the top of the reactor and the bottom port is provided at 1.5 cm upward from the bottom of the reactor. PVC filter media which is half of the PVC rings of length 1.5 cm, the external diameter of 1.5 cm and an internal diameter of 1.3 cm is filled up to 10 cm above the porous plate which is situated at 19 cm from the bottom of the reactor (Figure 1b).

PVC rings were chosen as packing media since its surface will retain additional biomass instead of the plain surface because of its high area, high porosity and low density. The large surface area of media improves the strong adhesion of microbial biomass on the packing media and also promotes the proper physical entrapment and bonding between biomass and media. The porous plate of 0.5 cm diameter pores is used for supporting the filter media and the diameter of the plate is equal to the internal diameter of the reactor (Figure 1c). Inlet tank (37 cm length, 23.5 cm width and 37 cm height) is used to store the wastewater sample, which is connected by the bottom inlet port of the reactor. The inlet tank is placed at some height (approx. 165 cm) from the bottom of the reactor. Height is provided for the inlet tank because no external pump is used as a feed pump; only gravitational flow is provided for the inlet flow. A valve is fitted in the inlet pipe for controlling the flow rate. The overall setup of

Figure 3. Seeding of the reactor

the reactor is placed in an environmental laboratory for the treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater at the pilot scale.

2.2 Operational method for anaerobic hybrid reactor

Graphical representation of upflow anaerobic hybrid reactor is shown in figure 2. After setup of the reactor, the bottom of the reactor is filled with 0.5 L of activated sludge (taken from working anaerobic sludge bed reactor in the slaughterhouse wastewater plant, Gazipur, Delhi) below the porous plate and close all four outlet ports. 1/10 diluted sample (1 L sample and 9 L tap water) fill in the reactor upto the second port from the top of the reactor for seeding purpose. Seeding is necessary for growing the anaerobic micro-organism in working environmental condition and it takes almost 10-15 days (Figure 3).

After seeding, the inlet tank is filled with a 1/10 diluted sample for the reactor's operation. 1/10 diluted sample was taken because of low efficiency or working efficiency is low of the reactor at the initial stage. So, the diluted sample was used but when the efficiency of the reactor will increase, the dilution ratio will increase (from 1/10 to 1/1) and at last, the sample (without dilution) is used to achieve the satisfactory results. Detention time is 24 hr for the reactor and the total volume of the reactor is 3.26 L, so the flow maintained by the inlet valve is 3.26 L/24 hr which equals to 11.31 mL/5 min. Flow through the inlet tank is very low and it is maintained by adjusting the valve by using

Figure 5. Removal of (a) phosphorus, (b) BOD and (c) alkalinity from slaughterhouse wastewater

35.27-76.007% in the operation period of the reactor.

3.4 Alkalinity and volatile acid (as CaCO₃ and acetic acid)

After finding the alkalinity and VFA, the ratio VFA/alkalinity is calculated and the value is most of the time below or near to 0.4 showing a favourable fermentation condition inside the reactor (Figures 5c and 6) [24].

3.5 TSS and VSS

From table 1, it is depicted that the removal efficiency of the reactor in terms of TSS (94.2%) and VSS (96.4%) is very high.

Figure 6. Volatile acid as (a) CaCO₃ and (b) acetic acid at inlet and outlet

Table 1. TSS and VSS at inlet and outlet

S.no	TSS (g/L)		VSS (g/L)	
	Inlet	Outlet	Inlet	Outlet
1	10.5	0.72	7.12	0.31
2	10.9	0.63	6.98	0.29
3	10.6	0.65	6.83	0.24
4	9.89	0.968	6.9	0.35
5	9.78	0.92	7.11	0.429
6	10.11	0.95	6.94	0.32
7	10.8	0.836	6.76	0.416

4. CONCLUSION

The upflow anaerobic hybrid reactor is used for the treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater at different dilutions (1/10, 1/6, 1/4, 1/1(undiluted)) at the pilot scale. PVC (polyvinyl chloride) is used as a filter media for treatment in the reactor. The detention time for the reactor was 24 hr. The flow of inlet, 135.72 mL/hr were the same throughout the period of treatment. Initially, 1/10 diluted sample was used as an influent to the reactor at COD loading of 9.281 kgCOD/m³ day and achieved COD removal efficiency upto 20.544%.

Then, 1/6 diluted sample was used with COD loading of 10.149 kgCOD/m³ day and achieved COD removal efficiency upto 35.05%. After this, 1/4 diluted samples were used as influent to the reactor with COD loading of 9.263 kgCOD/m³ day and achieved COD removal efficiency upto 61.91%. And finally, the undiluted sample was used as influent to the reactor with COD loading of 11.21 kgCOD/m³ day and achieved COD removal efficiency upto 73.32% and it is the maximum COD removal efficiency of reactor throughout the period. As discussed in the present study removal efficiency in terms of TSS (94.2%), VSS (96.4%), phosphorus (39.58%) and VFA (88.84%) were also determined in a specific time intervals and give satisfactory results. As the maximum COD removal efficiency of upflow anaerobic hybrid reactor using PVC as packing media is 73.32% which shows that slaughterhouse wastewater can be treated using this treatment unit. An additional treatment unit alongwith the upflow anaerobic packed bed reactor can be used to meet the standards given for disposal in river bodies.

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